

The Mismatching Between Universities Product And Labour Market Demands: The Challenges of Saudi Arabia Universities

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 19, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 23, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : High Education Institutions, Knowledge, Skills, Attitudes, Labor Market Needs</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5722531</p>	<p><i>This paper presents the results of a foresight study identified the Financial, Physical, Human, Intellectual and Digital resources challenges faced by Saudi universities. The previous universities challenges divert the focus on narrowing the gap between universities product and Labor Market demands. However, Data collection was gathered through interviews of twenty-five Saudi universities leaders in addition to designed web-based questionnaires that were distributed online to Saudi universities leaders and faculties members (SULFs) from different regions. The questions consisted of six sections aimed to identify the main Financial, Physical, Human, Intellectual and Digital challenges that Saudi universities should be overcome to deal with the new changes of business environments as well as narrow the gap between universities product and Labor Market employer's requirement. The reliability and validity of the survey were confirmed by Cronbach's alpha and the all data were examined using descriptive tests such as percentage, mean and standard deviation. Moreover, ANOVA and Correlation Matrix methods were also used to test the significant of differences in member's attitudes. The results of the study clearly emphasize on crucial needs and quick response to overcome all challenges in order to fulfil this new era of the rapid pace of Saudi labor market new changes. The recommendations of current study may be apply by academics leaders and faculties to set up future-oriented education curricula, policies and direction as well as narrow the gap between Saudi universities product and the local market demand.</i></p>

Introduction

The context in the labor market internationally is changing. Today, the most traditional education system does not help much to provide product match labor market demands. Yet, increase universities degree holders does not necessarily fulfill labor market needs at their level of qualifications (Brown, Lauder & Cheung, 2019). However, the mismatch between Saudi universities graduate's and career opportunities in the Saudi Arabia market remains a most important challenge. Despite many graduates being churned out for the job market, most of the graduates in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia are unable to find appropriate jobs because what they have studied in universities is not suitable to job demand (Kinani, 2020). Therefore, this paper aims to identify the most Financial, Physical, Human, Intellectual and Digital challenges faced by Saudi universities which maximize the barriers. Moreover, enhance the role of Saudi universities to overcome all challenges, and deal with the new changes of business environments, with full respect of the main factors draw the high education characteristics were Saudi ambitious 2030 vision and Saudi new High education system.

Kingdom Saudi Arabia high education system is an educational step that follows the secondary School. Universities either governmental or private. However, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has more than 30 public universities and around sixteen private universities. In addition, several community colleges, the majority of high education institutes are led by the government (Kinani, 2020). Moreover, Saudi governmental universities and colleges offer free of charge diploma and bachelor's degree for Saudi students plus a monthly payment during their studying period. However, in the first quarter of 2020, Saudi ministry of education have started to implement, the new universities education system aims to boost the universities independence through financially, administratively and academically. In other words, the SULFs will be able to approve their programs, budget and organization according to international development needs and job opportunities. Thus, the biggest advantages in such system will hope Saudi Arabia universities management to get rid of restrictions such as government bureaucracy, administrative work and they can set their brand name and academic standards. It's worth to maintain that, In 2016 Kingdom of Saudi Arabia launched the ambitious vision 2030 aims to bridging the gap between high education outcome and labor market requirement. Moreover, according

to Saudi education ministry report (2020) the vision 2030 targeted to have at least five universities, among the top 200 universities in international rankings.

Universities resources are essential for enhance education performance and researches value. It remains one of the strategic and tactical goals. Also, support universities leaders and faculties while providing academic program with the infrastructure they need in order to perform effectively (Weaver & Osterman, 2016). However, this research will emphasize in Financial, Physical, Human, Intellectual and Digital resources challenges of Saudi universities from SULFs perspectives. However, the following statements elaborate the definitions of selected university resources:

- Financial resources are the funds of the enterprise and intended for the implementation of Universities expenses. Most of the universities have financial resources on a regular basis. However, this study will emphasize in the number of Students Enrollment, Alternative financial resources, budgeting management, financial autonomy and Cost optimization.
- Physical Resources are considered as tangible assets, which the universities uses to create excellent learning environment to students. Physical resources may include the equipment, buildings, inventory, Workshops and furniture, which are extremely crucial for the universities to function properly.
- Human resources are considered as the most important assets of any universities. Expert leaders and faculty are important because they are the main stakeholders who are committed to the core academic program and democratic values. Thus, this paper will stressed the main factors, which enhance attracting and retaining the best talent, rising faculty's experience, Administrative Autonomy, lack of admission criteria and comply with Saudi 2030 vision.
- Intellectual resources are one of universities resources, which are non-physical and intangible in nature like curriculum innovation, university partnerships, talent leaders, expert faculties and research innovation.
- Digital resources are core skills for graduates entering the modern job market. This study aims to examine the availability of e-learning system and e-Library as well as the utilization of digital resources.

Methodology

The study had reviewed the Financial, Physical, Human, Intellectual and Digital resources challenges faced by Saudi universities, which resist narrow the gap between universities product and Labor Market demands. The research is based on the conceptual study and the data has been collected from the global secondary resources of information such as different international published papers, statistics, and books. In addition to present the results of a forecasting research shows the Financial, Physical, Human, Intellectual and Digital resources challenges from SULF perspective. The significance of the study lies in the fact that the obtained results would support Saudi universities leaders and education ministry decision-makers to overcome the current challenges. In addition to added great efforts to reduce the gap between the competencies demand and supply, which arises out of global labor market changes as well as Saudi 2030 vision.

a) Survey of Saudi universities leaders and faculties members

The online survey questionnaire was designed with the primary objectives to find the challenges faced by Saudi universities. The design of the survey has gone through different phases and pre-tests, which have resulted in reclassifying, eliminating, and rephrasing its elements. The resulting questionnaires are organized into six sections as follow:

Section I: Respondents' Characteristics: aimed to identify respondents' characteristics such as qualification, age, experience, Job title and university region.

Section II: Financial resources: intended to identify the main financial challenges of Saudi universities to align with the Saudi Vision 2030 objectives and narrow the gap between Saudi universities product and Labor Market employer's expectation.

Section III: Physical resources: intended to identify the main physical challenges of Saudi universities to align with the Saudi Vision 2030 objectives and narrow the gap between Saudi universities product and Labor Market demands.

Section IV: Human resources: intended to identify main Human resources challenges of Saudi universities to align with the Saudi Vision 2030 objectives and narrow the gap between Saudi universities product and labor market employer's expectation.

Section V: Intellectual resources: intended to identify Intellectual resources challenges of Saudi universities to align with the Saudi Vision 2030 objectives and narrow the gap between Saudi universities product and labor market demands.

Section VI: Digital resources: intended to identify Digital resources challenges of Saudi universities to align with the Saudi Vision 2030 objectives and narrow the gap between Saudi universities product and labor market employer's expectation.

The questionnaires were sent out to 400 SULFs from different region across the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Survey respondents were asked to assess each of six sections, based on five ranking-Likert rating scale- which enables comparative deductions. The collected data were analyzed wisely by using descriptive tests (mean, percentage, Correlation Matrix standard deviation, T test, P value and ANOVA). The internal consistency of the questionnaires same group elements was measured by Cronbach's alpha method and its content validity was tested based on expert reviews.

b) Interviews with Saudi universities leaders

The interview questions were prepared as per research objectives to find the challenges faced by Saudi universities, which disturb narrow the gap between universities product and Labor Market demands. The interviews have been conducted with twenty-five Saudi Arabia universities leaders from different region. The questions as follow: (1) At which extend Saudi universities outcome are matching with labor market employers expectation, (2) At which extend Saudi universities have the financial resources to meet labor market employer's needs (3) At which extend Saudi universities have the Physical resources to meet labor market employer's needs (4) At which extend Saudi universities has the human resources to meet labor market employer's needs, (5) At which extend Saudi universities has the Intellectual resources to meet labor market employer's needs, (6) At which extend Saudi universities has the Digital resources to meet labor market employer's needs.

Data analysis and results

Out of the 400 questionnaires sent, 121 replies were received from different universities across the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The questions consisted of six sections aiming to discover the challenges faced by Saudi universities, which disturb narrow the gap between universities product and Labor Market demands. The respondents were of different qualification, age, experience, job title and universities region.

Survey Validity

In order to test research survey, internal consistency has been verified by calculating Cronbach's alpha. It measures the internal consistency among a group of items combined to form a single scale and reflects the homogeneity of the survey data scale. A value of Cronbach's alpha if it is more than 0.7 shows homogeneity and consistency of the survey element. Yet, Table 1 shows the Cronbach's alpha coefficients. As shown, the results of the Cronbach's alpha range, from 0.791 to 0.903, illustrating the reliability.

TABLE 1. Overall Cronbach's Alpha, Means.

Questionnaire components	No.	Cronbach's alpha	Mean
Financial resources	5	0.859	3.02
Physical resources	5	0.791	2.52
Human resources	5	0.903	2.85
Intellectual resources	5	0.859	3.52
Digital resources	5	0.869	3.95

The survey's internal consistency also assessed through Pearson correlation coefficients between the terms of each universities challenges. The results are shown in Table number 9 indicate clearly that there is no significant correlation between items, even for negative ones.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The data gathered were examined using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) program. A descriptive statistical analysis using (mean, percentage, standard deviation, t-test and P-value) were utilized to describe the variable to answer the research question: "Which challenges should Saudi universities overcome to narrow the gap between universities product and Labor Market demands?" The SULFs answered the survey using scale ranging from one for strongly disagree, until five for Strongly Agree. The range between the max and min mean values was classified into five levels reflecting the respondents' attitudes towards the questionnaire in Table 2. The mean scores and standard deviation, Variance and P-values for the questionnaire components are offered in Table 3. As illustrated, all components ranked mean values between 2.85 and 3.95. Such result shows strong attitude of the participants towards the needs to overcome universities challenges.

TABLE 2. Mean Ranges and Participant Attitudes

Mean range	Respondent attitudes
Below 2.80	weak
2.80 to 3.60	Strong
Above 3.60	Very strong

TABLE 3. Overall means, variance, std. deviations and respondent's attitude

Questionnaire components	Mean	Std. Dev	Variance	P-value	Respondent's attitude
Financial resources	3.02	0.072	0.056	0.0038	strong
Physical resources	2.52	0.164	0.087		strong
Human resources	2.85	0.085	0.136		strong
Intellectual resources	3.52	0.124	0.078		strong
Digital resources	3.95	0.109	0.136		very strong

a) Respondent Profiles

The SULFs profiles are elaborated in Table 4. The SULFs from different education level, job titles, experience, ages and University regions. A careful examination shows that 84.3 % of the SULFs were more than 15 years of experience, and the majority of them (71.07 %) hold Assist Professor degree. It's worth to mention that (88.99%) of respondent were Faculties members and 66.12% of respondents ages ranged from 35 to 50 years old.

TABLE 4: Respondent Profiles

No.	Profile of Respondents		No.	P %
1	Job title	President / Vice President	7	5.79
		Section head/ Dean	16	13.22
		Faculties member	98	80.99
2	Education level	professor	9	7.44
		Associate Professor	26	21.49
		Assist Professor	86	71.07
3	Age (years)	less than 35	5	4.13
		35 to 50	80	66.12
		more than 50	36	29.75
4	Experience	less than 7	5	4.13
		11 to 15	14	11.57
		More than 15	102	84.30
5	University region	Eastern Region	35	28.93
		Western Region	41	33.88
		Central Region	45	37.19

Analysis of variance by (ANOVA), mean, p-value and t-test were used to determine if there are significant differences between the groups. An important question was raised in this paper: "Do the attitudes of participants vary based on the participant's Job title, education level, universities region?" A null hypothesis (H0) was set for the research as follows: "There are no significant differences in the way participants view the Financial, Physical, Human, Intellectual and Digital resources challenges faced by Saudi universities" The level of significance of the data is illustrated in terms of the p-value and/or mean as shown in following tables 5,6,7,8:

b) Attitudes of participants based on the Job title

The p-value is a result, calculated from a statistical test; it is used as a substitute for rejection points to provide the smallest level of significance at which the null hypothesis would be rejected. If p-value more than 0.05 will not considered significant and illustrate strong evidence for the null hypothesis. As shown in Table 5, the result of analysis gave p-values 0.00093 (<0.05), which shows significant differences in how participants based on the Job title view the Saudi universities challenges and the null hypothesis should be rejected.

TABLE 5: ANOVA for participant's attitudes with job title

Randomized blocks ANOVA				
Job title	Std. Dev	Mean	p-value	t-tests
President / Vice President	0.155	2.431	0.00093	0.00071
Section head/ Dean	0.215	3.471		
Faculties member	0.348	3.615		

c) Attitudes of participants based on University region

The mean is the most common value in a group of data. In statistics, it's measure central tendency of a probability distribution. However, Table Number 6 illustrations the correlation between Financial, Physical, Human, Intellectual and Digital resources challenges and University region's type. The mean of universities in Western Region in Financial resources slightly higher, and the mean for Eastern Region, Central region and Western Region of Digital resources are too high and almost quail, which indicates no statistically significant differences in how participants based on the University region, view the need of Digital resources. Nevertheless, the Eastern Region, Western Region and Central region are located between (0.195 to 0.345) which showed low standard deviation and all data are clustered around the mean.

TABLE 6: ANOVA for participants' attitudes with University region

University region	Financial resources	Physical resources	Human resources	Intellectual resources	Digital resources	Std. Dev
Eastern Region	2.874	2.252	2.998	3.598	3.898	0.195
Western Region	3.484	3.094	3.398	3.198	3.688	0.215
Central region	2.885	3.015	2.618	3.798	3.918	0.345

d) Attitudes of participants based on Education level

A t-test is a tool for assess the means of data using hypothesis testing. It is used to evaluate whether a single group differs from a known value, whether two groups differ from each other. However, if a t-test above 0.05 is not considered significant and shows strong evidence for the null hypothesis. As shown in Table 5, the data analysis gave p-values 0.0089 (<0.05), which indicates significant differences in how SULFs based on Education level view the universities challenges and the null hypothesis should be rejected.

TABLE 7: ANOVA for participant's attitudes with education level

Randomized blocks ANOVA				
Education level	Std. Dev	Mean	p-value	t-tests
Professor	0.215	2.894	0.0089	0.0041
Associate Professor	0.215	3.057		
Assist Professor	0.229	3.563		

e) Attitudes of participants based on SULFs Experience

The similar concept applied to approve there is no significant differences in how SULFs view the universities changes based on education level. The table 8 illustrations the correlation between Financial, Physical, Human, Intellectual and Digital resources challenges faced by Saudi universities and SULFs Experience. The mean for Financial, Physical, Human, Intellectual and Digital resources challenges with experience wise were fluctuated. In additional, the standard deviation for different SULFs experience are located between (0.202 to 0.287), which showed low standard deviation and data are clustered around the average.

TABLE 8: ANOVA for participants' attitudes with years of Experience

Experience	Financial resources	Physical resources	Human resources	Intellectual resources	Digital resources	Std. Dev
less than 35	3.185	3.865	3.095	4.398	4.552	0.202

35 to 50	3.242	2.582	2.758	3.432	3.958	0.273
more than 50	2.969	2.218	3.415	2.715	2.985	0.287

f) Financial, Physical, Human, Intellectual and digital resources challenges mean as per SULFs

Table number 9 shows the means for each survey questions of research survey. The lows scored were the challenges are Library, Budgeting management and Lecture hall and building readiness. While the highest challenges were exceed 3.60 are Lack of implementation, Curriculum innovation, Lack of interest, Partnerships, Availability of e-learning system, Availability of e- Library, Alternative financial resources, Number of Students Enrollment and Lack of knowledge.

TABLE 9: universities resources challenges based on all SULFs feedback

	#	Universities challenges	Mean	Std. Dev	Pearson Corr.
Financial resources	1	Number of Students Enrollment	3.637	0.876	0.075
	2	Alternative financial resources	3.682	0.786	0.190
	3	Budgeting management	2.050	0.778	0.310
	4	Financial autonomy	3.501	0.659	- 0.077
	5	Cost optimization	2.561	1.02	0.422
Physical resources	1	Library	2.037	0.125	0.084
	2	Laboratories	3.581	0.150	0.158
	3	Lecture hall and building	2.150	0.215	0.162
	4	furniture and facilities	2.654	0.157	0.205
	5	Workshops	3.521	0.352	0.315
Human resources	1	Number of Students Enrollment	3.637	0.876	0.075
	2	Alternative financial resources	3.682	0.786	0.190
	3	Budgeting management	2.050	0.778	0.310
	4	Financial autonomy	3.501	0.659	0.077
	5	Cost optimization	2.561	1.02	0.422
Intellectual resources	1	Curriculum innovation	4.157	1.249	- 0.065
	2	Partnerships	3.880	0.876	0.190
	3	Talent leaders	3.102	0.728	0.380
	4	Expert faculties member	3.201	0.559	0.047
	5	Research innovation	3.351	1.041	0.402
Digital resources	1	Availability of e-learning system	3.457	1.524	0.165
	2	Availability of e- Library	3.689	0.746	0.208
	3	Lack of knowledge	3.708	0.798	0.360
	4	Lack of implementation	4.275	0.810	- 0.047
	5	Lack of interest	3.981	1.002	0.422

RECOMENDATIONN AND CONCLUSION

Nevertheless, the role of SULFs is essential to fulfil the current demand of Saudi Arabia labor markets. According to the current research paper, the major challenges faced by Saudi universities are Lack of (interest, implementation and knowledge) in Digital resources, Curriculum innovation, difficulties to build Partnerships, unavailability of e- Library, discover alternative financial resources, huge Number of Students Enrollment.. Therefore, SULFs should be overcome all Financial, Physical, Human, Intellectual and Digital resources challenges in order to narrow the gap between universities product and Labor. Thus, research team concluded following recommendations to overcome the current universities challenges:

Enhance Digital resources implementation

- Conduct awareness to all Saudi universities leaders and faculties illustrate the importance of Digital resources to enhance education system and narrow the gap between universities product and Labor Market demands.
- Launch training and/or workshops programs for all Saudi universities leaders and faculties, associated with the latest update of Digital resources

- c) Tie the annual appraisal of Saudi universities leaders and faculties with utilizing Digital resources.
- d) Incorporates with third party to launch a new training program for existing universities workers to enhance the current work's Digitalization knowledge.

Curriculum innovation

- a) Re-evaluate the Curriculum objectives of Saudi universities and link the goals with satisfying local Labor Market needs
- b) Take the local and international job trends in consideration during re-evaluation stage of Saudi universities Curriculum.
- c) Cultivate the culture of innovation through universities curricula, campus life, faculties and technology.

Building Partnerships

- a) Develop strong feedback system between Saudi universities and local Labor Market employers aims to narrow the gaps between universities produce and Labor Market demands
- b) Establish new platform and frequent meeting aims to gather Saudi universities employers with human resource ministries leaders to identify the future job opportunities in order to alignment and collaboration
- c) Establish pilot projects by Saudi universities leaders to demonstrate the international best practices, and measuring the success of these pilots.
- d) Engaging Saudi Arabia universities graduate to addressing the barriers and challenges faced with hiring.
- e) Encourage Saudi Labor Market employees to conduct frequent Campaigns aims to raise awareness of and Promote Multiple Pathways to Well-Paying Jobs for All Saudi students.

Unavailability of e- Library

- a) Provide e- Library access for all Saudi Arabia universities students and faculties in one of international e- Library
- b) Establish training and/or workshops programs for all Saudi Arabia universities students and faculties and elaborate the importance of e- Library to enhance the education performance.

Discover alternative financial resources

- a) Utilize the new Saudi universities system opportunities by establish or invest in local or international companies
- b) Establish endowment programs to charge fees as imposing tuition fees for postgraduate programs, diplomas, training and educational courses,
- c) Establish new programs to charge fees for doing scientific research or consulting services
- d) Create programs to invest in Saudi universities facilities such as stadiums, auditoriums and halls.

Huge Number of Students Enrollment

- a) Reevaluate the current Number of Students Enrolled and provide solutions to minimize the Students such segregate the Students in morning and afternoon time
- b) Establish new criteria and standard to adjust number of student's enrollment as per university capabilities.
- c) Provide alternative high education programs such as on line learning or equivalent education

In conclusion, improve the alignment between universities product and the labour market demand required a concerted effort between Saudi ministries, universities leaders, local market employers and other stakeholders. Although Kingdom of Saudi Arabia Vision 2030 is committed to close the gap between universities produce and Labour Market demands. SULFs shall engage in continuous planning to overcome Financial, Physical, Human, Intellectual and Digital resources challenges and reform their curricula, programs and overall direction to comply with new Saudi business environments. Thus, Saudi universities leaders must think globally also develop strong students, which differentiates them from their competition, this will dramatically impact narrowing the gap positively (Ponnusamy, 2019). Yet, this research herein reflects the great potential to raise the quality of Saudi universities outcomes to match Labour Market needs by identifying the main challenges as per SULFs feedback with full respect of Saudi 2030 vision and Saudi High education new system.

REFERENCE

- A. Weaver and P. Osterman, 2016 "Skill Demands and Mismatch in U.S. Manufacturing," *Industrial and Labor Relations Review*, vol. 70, Jul. 2016, doi: 10.1177/0019793916660067.
- "Saudi Vision 2030." <https://vision2030.gov.sa/en/node> (accessed Aug.06, 2020), [Online]. Available http://vision2030.gov.sa/sites/default/files/report/Saudi_Vision2030_EN_2017.pdf.

- “Saudi Universities to Open Art, Theatre, Film Departments for First Time in History,” Ahramonline, June 16, 2020, accessed August 31, 2020, <http://english.ahram.org.eg/NewsContent/5/35/372258/Arts--Culture/Stage--Street/Saudi-universities-to-openart,-Theatre,-film-depa.aspx>.
- Mohammed Kinani, (2020) “Foreign Universities to Open Branch Campuses in Saudi Arabia” Arab News, October 30, 2019, accessed August 31, 2020, <https://www.arabnews.com/node/1576231/saudi-arabia>.
- Ponnusamy, L. D. (2019). Teacher Learning in Curriculum Innovation, the Unique Case for Embedded Learning.
- In Peters M., Heraud R. (Eds.), Encyclopedia of Educational Innovation. Singapore: Springer.
- Brown, P., Lauder, H., & Cheung, S. Y. (2019). Fractures in the education–Economy relationship: The end of the skill bias technological change research programme? Oxford Review of Economic Policy, 34(3), 495–515. [Crossref], [Web of Science ®], [Google Scholar]

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